

EVALUATION OF POTASSIUM LEVELS IN CONGESTIVE HEART FAILURE PATIENTS: A CASE CONTROL STUDY

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Abstract

Hyper and hypokalemia is a common ionic imbalance in patient with heart failure. Increased death and hospital stay is common in patients with HF and chronic kidney disease (CKD) who have hypokalaemia. As hyper or hypokalaemia are potentially hazardous and frequent complication in heart failure patient it is important to identify patients who are at increased risk for hypo and hyperkalaemia. The objective of this study was to identify socio-demographic characteristics, etiological factors and risk factors for hypo/hyperkalaemia in newly diagnosed patients with heart failure. Heart failure patient details were retrospectively identified from medical records using ICD 10 code I50.22. Ethical Committee approval was obtained before start of the study. Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria patient's files was reviewed for demographic information, clinical data, laboratory parameters, medication history and drugs prescribed and was entered in case record forms (CRF). The obtained data was analyzed by using SPSS software using Chi square test and Logistic regression and expressed as odds ratio (OR). Our finding may help to better identify patients with heart failure most likely to benefit from careful monitoring of serum potassium level. Improved vigilance is needed during start of treatment with certain classes of drugs and co-morbid illness.

Key words: Chronic kidney disease, Hyperkalemia, Hypokalemia, Heart failure

Introduction

Hyperkalaemia may result in the multiple organ dysfunction and cardiac arrest which has high mortality rate in hospital (1). HF patients with CVD on antihypertensive therapy have increased cause for mortality and hospitalization (2). When it is associated with arrhythmias, risk becomes life threatening (3). Accordingly its risk increases in patients with HF and CKD. Un-recognized hypokalaemia leads to iatrogenic death.

Diuretic drug treatment for hypertension or HF usually involves hypokalaemia. Loop diuretics and digoxin treatment may result in the common and unlikely side effect known as hypokalaemia (4). Increased death and hospital stay is common in patients with HF and CKD who have hypokalaemia (5). Once CHF is advanced enough, the renal function starts to decline to considerable increase in risk of developing hyperkalaemia. Patients with this risk include those with potassium excretion that has already been affected, such as the older population and patients with renal disorders and diabetes (6). In advanced CHF patient with diabetes mellitus, the propensity to develop hyperkalaemia may be even more likely.

Cardio toxicity can first happen and needs to be addressed urgently. Additionally, major changes in the Congestive Heart Failure (CHF) drug regimens which are essential to the effective treatment of CHF often happen after hyperkalaemia (7). In elderly diabetic patients and those who received drug that block renin and angiotensin II production or action, aldosterone production is reduced. Thus, these groups are particularly susceptible to the development of hyperkalaemia, due to potassium excretion that is already impaired as a result of age or disease - related decreases of glomerular filtration rate (8).

Hence, potassium levels need to be supervised in all patients with new diagnoses of hypertension, heart failure, or any disease that requires RAAS treatment with a diuretic or agents like beta - blockers, angiotensin inhibitors, blockers of angiotensin receptors, inhibitors of vasopeptidase, or a number of K⁺- sparing agents (9)

Research methodology:

Study Site: Tertiary care Hospital

Study design: Case-control study.

Study period: August 2018 to March 2019

Ethical Approval:

The protocol for this study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Hospital.

Sample Size: 1035 Patients.

Study criteria:

- Hypokalaemia cases: Heart failure patients with serum potassium levels < 3.6 mEq/L
- Hyperkalaemia cases: Heart failure patients with serum potassium levels > 5.2 mEq/L
- Controls: Heart failure patients with serum potassium levels between 3.6–5.2 mEq/L

Inclusion criteria:

- All heart failure patients with serum potassium levels of < 3.6 mEq/L and > 5.2 mEq/L
- Patients admitted under cardiology during 2013-2017

Exclusion criteria:

- The patients whose serum potassium levels were not checked.
- Lost patient files

Data source:

Patient Case Records, online clinical laboratory reports.

Study materials

- ✓ Case report form (CRF). It consists of (demographics, clinical information, lab parameters, history of medicine, prescribed medicines, type, duration, severity and co-morbidity, patient conditions).

Operation modality

- ✓ Heart failure patient details were retrospectively identified over a 6 months period from MRD files using ICD 10 code I50.22. Ethical Committee approval was obtained prior to start of the study.
- ✓ Control group included heart failure patients with normal potassium levels. Cases included heart failure patients developing hyper or hypokalaemia during the treatment.
- ✓ Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria patient's files were reviewed for demographic information, clinical data, laboratory parameters, medication history and

drugs prescribed and was entered in case record forms (CRF). Type, duration, severity of illness and co morbid conditions of the patients were collected and recorded in the CRF.

Data Analysis

Continuous data was expressed Mean \pm SD. Nominal data expressed in frequency and percentage. Association between risk factors with hyper/hypokalaemia was assessed by Chi square test and Logistic regression and expressed as odds ratio (OR). All statistical analysis were carried out using SPSS software version 20.0

Results

Table 1: Demographic and life style characteristics of patients of case (hypo/hyperkalaemia) and control

Parameter	Total (n=804)	Cases (n =346)		Control (n = 458)
		Hypokalaemia (n =194)	Hyperkalaemia (n= 152)	Normal K+levels
Age (Mean\pmSD)	57.2 \pm 17.8	58.7 \pm 15.6	56.3 \pm 20.7	56.8 \pm 17.7
Length of hospital stay (Mean\pmSD)	7.0 \pm 4.9	8.0 \pm 5.7	8.1 \pm 5.5	6.3 \pm 4.1
Age category				
• ≤ 5 , n (%)	26(3.2%)	2(1%)	8(5.3%)	16(3.5%)
• 6-10, n (%)	2(0.2%)	----	1(0.7%)	1(0.2%)
• 11-30, n (%)	38(4.7%)	10(5.2%)	10(6.6%)	18(3.9%)
• 31-60, n (%)	364(45.3%)	93(47.9%)	54(35.5%)	217(47.4%)
• 61-90, n (%)	369(45.9%)	89(45.9%)	77(50.7%)	203(44.3%)
• ≥ 91 , n (%)	5(0.6%)	----	2(1.3%)	3(0.7%)
Gender, n(%)				

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Males,n(%) • Females,n (%) 	512(63.7%)	110(56.7%)	103(67.8%)	299(65.3%)
	292(36.3%)	84(43.3%)	49(32.2%)	159(34.7%)
Smoking,n(%)	13(1.6%)	2(1%)	4(2.6%)	7(1.5%)
Alcoholism, n (%)	26(3.2%)	5(2.6%)	8(5.3%)	13(2.8%)
Tobaccochewer,n(%)	6(0.7%)	2(1%)	1(0.7%)	3(0.7%)
Smoker+Alcoholic,n(%)	16(2%)	1(0.5%)	6(3.9%)	9(2%)
Reformedsmoker+alcoholic,n(%)	10(1.2%)	2(1%)	5(3.3%)	3(0.7%)
Tobacco chewer+alcoholic,n(%)	2(0.2%)	1(0.5%)	----	1(0.2%)
Mortality,n(%)				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alive • Dead 	742(92.3%)	176(90.7%)	137(90.1%)	429(93.7%)
	62(7.7%)	18(9.3%)	15(9.9%)	29(6.3%)

Figure1.Distribution o fheart failure patients based on hyperkalaemia and hypokalaemia

Table2:Co-morbidities in study population

isease	Total (n = 804)	Cases (n=346)		Control (n= 458)
	n (%)	Hypokalaemia, n=(194)	Hyperkalaemia, n= (152)	
Hypertension	73(9.1%)	28(14.4%)	7(4.6%)	38(8.3%)
IHD	41(5.1%)	7(3.6%)	6(3.9%)	28(6.1%)
T2 DM	77(9.6%)	18(9.3%)	16(10.5%)	18(9.3%)
RHD	18(2.2%)	4(2.1%)	3(2%)	11(2.4%)
HTN+Dm	106(13.2%)	25(12.9%)	30(19.7%)	52(11.4%)
COPD+IHD	11(1.4%)	-----	2(1.3%)	9(2%)
DM+HTN+BA+TB	11(1.4%)	3(1.5%)	2(1.3%)	6(1.3%)
IHD+HTN	21(2.6%)	5(2.6%)	2(1.3%)	14(3.1%)
IHD+T2DM+HTN	37(4.6%)	5(2.6%)	5(3.3%)	27(5.9%)
Dm+IHD	18(2.2%)	5(2.6%)	2(1.3%)	11(2.4%)
IHD+T2DM+CKD+ HTN	25(3.1%)	3(1.5%)	7(4.6%)	15(3.3%)
Others	100(12.4%)	23(11.8%)	24(15.9%)	52(11.2%)
None	266(33.1%)	68(35.1%)	46(30.3%)	152(33.2%)

Table3: Past medication history in study population.

Medications	Total (n = 804)	Cases (n = 346)		Control (n= 458)
	n (%)	Hypokalaemia, n=(194)	Hyperkalaemia, n= (152)	
Antidiabetics	33(4.1%)	6(3.1%)	10(6.6%)	17(3.7%)
Antibiotics	6(0.7%)	3(1.5%)	1(0.7%)	2(0.4%)
Antihypertensive	5(0.6%)	1(0.5%)	1(0.7%)	3(0.7%)
Diuretics	4(0.5%)	1(0.5%)	-----	3(0.7%)
CCB	9(1.1%)	1(0.5%)	2(1.3%)	6(1.3%)
Digoxin	3(0.4%)	1(0.5%)	-----	2(0.4%)

Aspirin	9(1.1%)	---	2(1.3%)	7(1.5%)
CCB+ Diuretics+ Aspirin+atorvastatin+ Antidiabetic	10(1.2%)	3(1.5%)	4(2.6%)	3(0.7%)
Diuretics+CCB	15(1.9%)	3(1.5%)	2(1.3%)	10(2.2%)
Antidiabetic+Diuretics	13	4(2.1%)	4(2.6%)	9(2%)
Aspirin+Antidiabetics+CCB	13(1.6%)	1(0.5%)	2(1.3%)	10(2.2%)
Others	18(2.4%)	8(4.3%)	6(4.1%)	2(0.4%)
None	662(82.3%)	162(83.5%)	118(77.6%)	382(83.4%)

Table-4:Association of risk factors(drugs)withhypokalaemia.

Factors	Oddsratio	95% CI	Pvalue
Alphaand Betablocker	1.853	0.936-3.669	0.08
Digoxin	1.417	0.998-2.012	0.05
Aspirin/acetylsalicylicacid+ Atorvastatin+Clopidogrel	0.407	0.190-0.872	0.02
Torsemide	1.425	0.944-2.151	0.92

Table5:Association of risk factors(drugs)with hyper kalaemia.

Factors	Oddsratio	95% CI	Pvalue
Spirolactone	2.101	1.243-3.551	0.01
Furosemide+Spirolactone	1.790	0.161-2.760	0.05
UFH	0.609	0.368-1.009	0.05

Discussion

Heart failure is a clinical condition resulting in a low standard of living, high morbidity and high mortality. Co - morbidities often lead to heart failure and aggravate the decline in standard of life and clinical results. The patho-physiological processes underlying the interactivity of heart failure with co - morbid conditions are complex (10).

In this study, Male preponderance (512, 63.7%)was observed. There appears to be more male patients (369, 45.9%)in the 61 - 90 age category. Evidently, the hyperkalaemia group observed more patients with both diabetes mellitus and hypertension (30, 19.7%).This study reported, hyperkalaemia patients had longer duration of hospital stay(8.1 ± 5.5 days)comparatively than hypokalaemia(8.0 ± 5.7 days).Relatively, mortality rate was found higher in hyperkalaemia(15, 9.9%) group. Hence, the descriptive analysis of past medicines revealed that patients with hyperkalaemia (10, 6.6%) had higher anti-diabetic drug usage compared to patients with hypokalaemia (6, 3.1%).Similar results were observed in the study by Desai as et al. wherein, male gender ≥ 75 years were more prone to developing hyperkalaemia (11).The result was

corroborated in a study by Jain N et al wherein, prolonged stay in hospital and the higher mortality rate were observed with cardio-vascular diseases(hypertension and heart failure) and DM (12).

In this study, Digoxin was found to be a risk factor with an odds ratio [OR: 1.417; CI: 0.998-2.012] which resulted in significant development of hypokalaemia. An article published by Bielecka-Dabrowa A details about, hypokalaemia which has become a common and despised residual effect with digoxin therapy, explaining enhanced neuro-hormonal activity or progression of the disease could also be highlighted with the low K(+) serum of HF.

In this analysis, Spironolactone was found to be a risk factor for hyperkalaemia with an odds ratio [OR: 2.101; CI: 1.243-3.551].The study by Desai AS et al showed increased risk of hyperkalaemia with spironolactone therapy. Progressing age, male gender, renal insufficiency, diabetes, or combined RAAS obstruction increases the occurrence of hyperkalaemia (13). Similarly, an article by Viyakumar S et al also reported a particularly increased risk of chronic or recurrent hyperkalaemia in patients with renin- angiotensin-aldosterone system inhibitors (RAASi).The study also examines barriers to guideline - mediated RAASi patterns in patients posing high risk of hyperkalaemia.

Conclusion

Our finding may help to better identify patients with heart failure most likely to benefit from careful monitoring of serum potassium level. Improved vigilance is needed during start of treatment with certain classes of drugs and co-morbid illness.

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